

Open-ended Knowledge Tracing for Programming Exercises

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge tracing refers to the problem of estimating each student’s knowledge component/skill mastery level from their past responses to questions in educational applications. One direct benefit knowledge tracing methods provide is the ability to predict each student’s performance on the future questions. However, one key limitation of most existing knowledge tracing methods is that they treat student responses to questions as binary-valued, i.e., whether the responses are correct or incorrect. Response correctness analysis/prediction is easy to navigate but loses important information, especially for open-ended questions: the exact student responses can potentially provide much more information about their knowledge states than only response correctness. In this paper, we present our first exploration into open-ended knowledge tracing (OKT), i.e., the analysis and prediction of students’ open-ended responses to questions in the knowledge tracing setup. We detail OKT’s application to the domain of computer science education with programming exercises. We conduct a series of quantitative and qualitative experiments to test the boundaries of OKT on the real-world dataset for the Second CSEDM Data Challenge.

1. INTRODUCTION

Knowledge tracing (KT) [7] refers to the problem of estimating student mastery of concepts/skills/knowledge components from their responses to questions/items and using these estimates to predict their future performance. KT methods mainly consist of two essential components: a *knowledge update* component that updates student knowledge estimates given their most recent observed response, and a *response prediction* component to predict their response to a future question [6, 11, 15, 25, 26, 27, 36, 37].

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One common property for almost all existing KT methods is that they only analyze and predict *binary-valued* student responses to questions, i.e., the *correctness* of the response; the response prediction component is often a simple binary classifier. As a result, one can broadly apply KT methods to any common types of questions: multiple-choice, short-answer, and even open-ended ones, as long as student responses are graded. There exist few KT methods for predicting non-binary-valued responses such as option tracing [12], which predicts the exact option students select on each multiple-choice question. In general, one can use polytomous IRT models [22] as the response prediction component in KT methods to predict categorical-valued (such as options in multiple-choice questions) and ordinal-valued (such as partial credit) responses [17, 34].

Unfortunately, analyzing and predicting binary-valued graded student response has a significant limitation: it does not make use of the *exact* question and student response, especially for open-ended questions. Students’ open-ended responses to such questions contain rich, meaningful information on their knowledge states, e.g., having a “buggy rule” [3], exhibiting a certain misconception [9, 10, 32], or a general lack of mastery of certain skills [1], which may not be captured by response correctness. This limitation may prevent KT methods from extracting knowledge estimates that reflect specific errors and making personalized recommendations that help students correct these errors.

Recent advances in neural language models, especially generative ones, are capable of problem solving in certain domains [4, 8]. In these domains, it is possible to use these models to predict students’ full open-ended responses via *generation*. An especially relevant domain is computer science education and programming exercises, where text-to-code capabilities offered by models such as CodeX [5] can generate short chunks of codes from natural language instructions. Open-ended response predictions can potentially be highly useful in these domains for hint generation [23, 28, 31] and error diagnostics. Existing works only use these models to encode student code into vectors as *input* to KT methods rather than using open-ended responses in *loss functions* to train the model [21, 35, 39].

1.1 Contributions

In this paper, we present the first attempt at extending KT methods to both analyze and predict open-ended student responses to questions in computer science education. Our

contributions can be summarized as follows:

- First, we define the open-ended knowledge tracing (OKT) framework, a novel, generic framework that analyzes and predicts open-ended student responses. We ground OKT in the specific domain of computer science education where students submit responses, i.e., code, to open-ended programming exercise questions. We address the key technical challenge of fusing the knowledge update component in KT methods with code generation models, treating student code prediction as a *controlled generation* problem. We also show that OKT is compatible with several popular KT methods for binary-valued student responses.
- Second, we perform extensive quantitative and qualitative experiments on a real-world student code dataset used in the second CSEDM challenge¹. We show that OKT is capable of capturing variations and specific errors in student code in their knowledge states and making reasonably accurate predictions of actual student-submitted code.

2. OKT FOR COMPUTER SCIENCE EDUCATION

Figure 1 illustrates the three OKT components designed for the CS education domain, visualized for a single student code submission. Our key technical challenges are (i) how to represent and combine the programming questions and students’ code submissions (knowledge representation, Section 2.1) and use them to update the students’ knowledge states (knowledge update, Section 2.2); (ii) how to combine the knowledge state with the question prompt to generate student code (response generation, Section 2.3); and (iii) how to efficiently perform optimization to train the OKT components (Section 2.4). Next, we address the above challenges and describe our design choices for each OKT component for CS education.

2.1 Knowledge Representation

Question Representation: Question prompts in programming assignments are usually in natural language. We thus use a pre-trained neural language model to convert them into embedding vectors. We adopt the popular GPT-2 [29] for prompt representation: Given a prompt p , GPT-2 tokenizes it into a sequence of M word tokens, where each token has an embedding $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^K$. For GPT-2, the dimension of these embeddings is $K = 768$. This procedure produces a sequence of token embeddings $\{\bar{\mathbf{p}}_1, \bar{\mathbf{p}}_2, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{p}}_M\}$. We then average the embeddings of each prompt token to get our prompt embedding $\mathbf{q} = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\bar{\mathbf{p}}_m}{M}$ where the average is computed element-wise on vectors.

Code Representation: In order to preserve both semantic and syntactic properties of programming code in the embeddings, we utilize ASTNN [38], a popular tool for code representation, following prior work [21, 24]. We first parse a student-submitted response code into an abstract syntax tree (AST). We then split each full AST into a sequence of non-overlapping statement trees (ST-trees) through pre-order traversal. Each ST-tree contains a statement node

¹<https://sites.google.com/ncsu.edu/csedm-dc-2021/>

Figure 1: An illustration of applying OKT to students’ code submissions for programming questions in computer science education scenarios. We update the current knowledge state \mathbf{h}_t using past question p_t and actual student code x_t and combine it with the next problem statement p_{t+1} to generate our prediction of the actual student code \hat{x}_{t+1} .

as the root and its corresponding AST nodes as children. We then pass the ST-trees through a recurrent statement encoder to obtain embedding vectors and use a bidirectional gated recurrent unit network [2] to capture the naturalness of the statements and further enhance the capability of the recurrent layer. Eventually, we apply a max-pooling layer to capture the most important semantics for each dimension of the embedding. We denote this process as $\mathbf{c} = \text{ASTNN}(\mathbf{x})$, where \mathbf{x} is the student-submitted code and \mathbf{c} is its code embedding vector, which we use as input to the knowledge update component. We refer readers to [38] for more details on ASTNN.

2.2 Knowledge Update

We use a long short-term memory (LSTM) model [13] to update a student’s knowledge state given their previous response at the last time step. Instead of one-hot embeddings for questions and responses or more sophisticated, graph-based embeddings that rely on question/concept IDs [27], we use the combination of the question prompt and code embeddings detailed above as the input to our knowledge update component. Our knowledge update component can

be summarized as $h_t = \text{LSTM}(h_{t-1}, \mathbf{q}_t, \mathbf{c}_t)$, where h_t is the student’s knowledge state at time step t . We will use h_t as input to the response generation component to predict actual student code submissions. As we show in our experiments (see Section 3), we can leverage any existing KT method as the knowledge update component.

2.3 Response Generation

We now turn our attention to the response generation component, the most important component of OKT. We use GPT-2 as our base generative model to fine-tune a text-to-code model P_Θ with parameter Θ on our dataset (we detail the reason for this choice in Section 2.5). We choose language models over other code generation approaches since their text-to-code generation pipeline suits OKT well.

Our key technical challenge is how to use knowledge states as *control* in the code generation model to make personalized code predictions for each student. At time step t , GPT-2 tokenizes the question prompt p_t into a sequence of M tokens as input to the model, with original token embeddings $\{\bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(1)}, \bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(2)}, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(M)}\}$, where $\bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(m)} \in \mathbb{R}^K$. Our approach for injecting student knowledge states into the code generation model is to replace these token embeddings with *knowledge-adjusted* embeddings using an *alignment* function, i.e., $\mathbf{p}_t^{(i)} = f(\bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(i)}, \mathbf{h}_t)$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$. Then we obtain our final input embeddings to GPT-2 as

$$\{\mathbf{p}_t^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{p}_t^{(M)}\} = \{f(\bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(1)}, \mathbf{h}_t), \dots, f(\bar{\mathbf{p}}_t^{(M)}, \mathbf{h}_t)\}.$$

Intuitively, this (possibly learnable) *alignment function* aligns the space of knowledge states with the space of question prompt text. Thus, knowledge states are responsible for predicting different code submitted to the same question by different students. We found that a linear combination of knowledge states and token embeddings performs best.

Given the student-submitted code tokens $x = \{x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots, x^{(N)}\}$ (we remove the time step index t for now for clarity and N denotes the number of code tokens) and the input question prompt token embeddings $\{\mathbf{p}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{p}^{(M)}\}$, the generative model for the student’s submitted code is

$$x \sim P_\Theta(x | \{\mathbf{p}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{p}^{(M)}\}), \quad (1)$$

where Θ denotes the set of parameters in the response prediction component, including both the text-to-code generation language model parameters and (when applicable) learnable parameters in the alignment function $f(\cdot)$. Since GPT-2 is an autoregressive language model, we can further decompose Eq. 1 into

$$x \sim \prod_{j=1}^N P_\Theta \left(x^{(j)} | \{\mathbf{p}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{p}^{(M)}\}, \{x^{(j')}\}_{j'=1}^{j-1} \right), \quad (2)$$

where $x^{(j)}$ denotes the j^{th} code token.

2.4 Optimization

During the training process, we jointly optimize the parameters of the knowledge update model and the response generation model; we keep the knowledge representation encoders E_1 and E_2 fixed. The objective for one student is simply the negative log-likelihood/cross entropy loss for all

code tokens, i.e.,

$$Loss = \sum_{j=1}^N -\log P_\Theta \left(x^{(j)} | \{\mathbf{p}^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{p}^{(M)}\}, \{x^{(j')}\}_{j'=1}^{j-1} \right) \quad (3)$$

while the total training objective sums this loss over all students.

2.5 Pre-training Models

Before training OKT, we pre-train its knowledge update component using the binary-valued correctness prediction loss with question and code embeddings as input, following [21, 39]. We also pre-train the response generation component to adapt GPT-2 to the text-to-code task with actual code. Since we cannot directly use CodeX [5] due to our need to adjust the input embeddings with student knowledge states, we use a similar pre-training strategy to fine-tune a standard GPT-2 model on the Funcom dataset [18], which contains 2.1 million Java code snippets together with textual descriptions in natural language.

3. EXPERIMENTS

We now present a series of quantitative and qualitative experiments to explore the capabilities of our proposed OKT approach for programming questions on a real-world dataset with student coding exercises. We first introduce the dataset and various quantitative metrics on which we will evaluate our method. **We emphasize that OKT is a completely new task and there is no prior work to compare with.** Finally, we present qualitative evaluation results to illustrate that our OKT method (i) learns meaningful structures of the students’ knowledge and (ii) generates coding solutions that, although not always exactly matching the students’ solutions, capture students’ coding patterns and types of mistakes they make.

Dataset. We use the dataset from the CSEDM Data Challenge, henceforth referred to as the **CSEDM dataset**.² To our knowledge, this is the only college-level, publicly-available dataset *with students’ actual code submissions*. The dataset contains 246 college students’ full submissions on each of the 50 programming assignments over the course of an entire semester. Instead of predicting the correctness of the last 20 problems given the previous answers for a student, which is the goal of the CSEDM Data Challenge, we repurpose this dataset for our task of open-ended knowledge tracing. Here, for each student, we would like to predict the student’s next *full code solution*, instead of its correctness, given the student’s history of solving the programming assignments. The dataset contains rich textual information on the problem prompt and the students’ code answers as well as other relevant metadata such as each problem’s knowledge components and the error messages returned by the compiler, if the students’ solution resulted in an error.

Evaluation Metrics. Evaluating generative models is generally a challenging problem. In the context of predicting students’ code submissions, we need a variety of different metrics to fully understand the effectiveness of OKT. We thus use two types of evaluation metrics. First, we need metrics that can measure OKT’s ability to predict student

²The dataset is referred to as “CodeWorkout data Spring 2019” accessed via DataShop (ps1cdatashop.web.cmu.edu).

setting	KT model	CodeBLEU \uparrow	Dist-1 \uparrow	Test Loss \downarrow
first submission	DKT	0.563	0.388	0.215
	AKT	0.576	0.395	0.200
	DKVMN	0.577	0.395	0.202
all submissions	DKT	0.545	0.388	0.137
	AKT	0.565	0.396	0.133
	DKVMN	0.519	0.388	0.145

Table 1: Student code prediction performance for OKT on the CSEDM dataset. Using DKT, AKT, and DKVMN as the knowledge update component result in similar performance, with AKT slightly outperforming the other two.

code on the test set after training. For this purpose, we use two metrics, including the average **test loss** computed using OKT methods with the best validation loss during training. The other metric is **CodeBLEU** [30], a variant of the classic BLEU metric adapted to code, which measures the similarity between predicted code and actual student code. Second, we need metrics that can measure the diversity of the generated code since we do not want the OKT methods to memorize typical student codes in the training data. For this purpose, we use the **dist- N** metric [19] that computes the ratio of unique N -grams in the generations over all N -grams. We choose $N = 1$ in this work. We acknowledge that there are other important evaluation metrics, such as those related to code execution; however, we cannot use them since the CSEDM dataset does not contain test cases for each programming question.

Experimental Setup We consider two experimental settings in our experiments that are similar but arguably capture different aspects of OKT. First, we analyze all code submissions from each student, including multiple consecutive attempts at the same question. This setting is used by most existing KT methods and traces students’ knowledge evolution while they gradually build up their code. Therefore, in this setting, knowledge states capture not only a student’s mastery of different coding concepts but also their ability to correct errors through debugging. Second, we also analyze only their first attempt at each question, ignoring later attempts. This setting is also used in the literature to predict correctness on first attempt [16] where consecutive time steps correspond to different questions. Therefore, in this setting, knowledge states mostly capture a student’s mastery of coding concepts. We choose to not use the final attempt since most students were able to write correct code in their final attempt at questions in the CSEDM dataset.

3.1 Quantitative Results

Table 1 shows the quantitative results evaluating OKT on the CSEDM dataset comparing DKT [27], AKT [11], and DKVMN [37] as the knowledge update component. We see that these KT methods perform similarly with each other, with AKT slightly outperforming the other two methods on most metrics in both experimental settings. DKT’s performance is consistent across both settings, whereas DKVMN performs better when predicting students’ first code submissions to each question than when predicting all code submissions. These results suggest that DKT and AKT are effective models for the knowledge update component of

OKT since DKT is simple and efficient while AKT achieves the overall best performance at the expense of a more complicated model architecture requiring more computational resources. Across the two experimental settings, analyzing students’ first submissions leads to much higher test loss than analyzing all submissions while performance on the other two metrics does not vary much. These results can be explained by our observation that students rarely make substantial changes to their code across different submissions, often making minor tweaks; therefore, predicting a later code submission given previous submissions becomes an easier task than predicting the first submission to a new question.

Overall, we observe that OKT is able to predict actual student code reasonably well; in terms of CodeBLEU, OKT with AKT as its KT model outperforms the simple baseline of majority student code by about 0.08; as a reference, the CodeBLEU value for the third example in Table 3 is 0.65, which is 0.08 higher than for the average performance of OKT. This observation suggests that despite OKT being able to capture major variations in student code, there is plenty of room for improvement on student code prediction.

3.2 OKT Framework Design Choices

We conduct an ablation study to understand how each design choice in OKT impacts its performance on predicting student code submissions. For this experiment, we analyze only the first code submission to each question made by every student and use DKT as the base KT model for knowledge update. We compare four different model design aspects: First, we compare different **alignment functions** between knowledge states and prompt token embeddings in the response generation component, including adding the two, averaging them, using a (learnable) weighted average, and a (learnable) linear combination. Second and third, we test whether **knowledge update component pre-training** and **response generation component pre-training** are effective. Fourth, we compare whether using a **multi-task** training objective where we add the typical correctness prediction loss to the code prediction loss in Eq. 3 during OKT training leads to improved code prediction accuracy.

Table 2 shows the results of the ablation studies. First, we see that aligning the knowledge state space with the prompt token embedding space with a learnable linear function appears to be the most effective, although other alignment functions are only slightly worse. Second, we see that pre-training the knowledge update and response generation components result in significant improvements in OKT’s code prediction performance. This result suggests that existing KT methods for response correctness prediction are useful in warm-starting OKT training, while fine-tuning pre-trained LMs on actual student code helps code prediction significantly.

The unusually high diversity scores when the knowledge update and response generation components are not pre-trained is due to their inability to generate coherent code, as reflected in their low CodeBLEU scores. Finally, we observe that a multi-task OKT training objective improves code prediction performance. This result suggests that like many other applications, multi-task learning with multiple objectives helps us learn better representations of data, i.e., the knowledge state representations in OKT.

		CodeBLEU \uparrow	Dist-1 \uparrow	Test Loss \downarrow
Combine Method	add	0.550	0.390	0.217
	average	0.541	0.390	0.218
	weight	0.549	0.389	0.217
	linear	0.563	0.388	0.215
Pre-train KT	yes	0.549	0.387	0.217
	no	0.495	0.409	0.326
Pre-train GPT	yes	0.549	0.387	0.217
	no	0.176	0.480	0.967
Multi-task	yes	0.593	0.406	0.399
	no	0.563	0.388	0.215

Table 2: Ablation studies comparing various OKT setups. In general, linearly combining knowledge states and the prompt token embeddings, pre-training both knowledge update and response generation components, and using a multi-task loss improve OKT performance.

3.3 Qualitative Results

We show that the knowledge states learned by OKT capture the variation in the content and structure of student code submissions and effectively trace students’ multiple attempts when responding to each question. Figure 2 visualizes the learned knowledge states (projected to a 2-dimensional space via t-SNE [33]) and corresponding student code for a question. We see that there are distinct clusters in these knowledge states that correspond to different student code. We can also zoom in into two areas in the knowledge state space, together with the corresponding actual student code submissions. We clearly see that the codes within each cluster share similar structural and syntactic properties and that codes from different clusters differ significantly. This result suggests that the OKT-learned knowledge state space *aligns* with actual student code submissions.

We can also track the knowledge state trajectories for two students responding to this question. The colors in these two figures represent knowledge states that correspond to incorrect, partially correct and fully correct codes at different time steps. We see that both students start with a wrong solution. However, one student gradually proceeded to the correct solution after a few edits, whereas the other student got stuck after a few unsuccessful edits and eventually gave up on solving this prompt. We also show four selected submissions by each student during their response process, further illustrating how the first student made steady progress, i.e., adding the return statement (first two code submissions) and correcting logic (last two code submissions), and how the second student got stuck, i.e., making reasonable changes initially but then some repetitive edits.

3.4 Case Study: Knowledge-aware Predictions of Students’ Code Submissions

We now use a case study to demonstrate OKT’s ability to predict student-submitted code. Similar to most existing text-to-code models [14, 20], exact prediction of the actual student code is very difficult. However, OKT can still be effective in capturing student’s coding styles and even predicting some error types with the help of the learned knowledge states. The top two rows in Table 3 shows the predicted

code versus the actual student code for two students on the same question. We see that even though the two selected students write code in very different ways, our predicted codes are able to follow their structure, capturing their habits to use *while* and *for* loops. The middle example shows that even though calling the *concat* function is not commonly found in students’ responses to this question (only 1% of the submissions do so), OKT is still able to predict it for the student. This example suggests that OKT can capture both code structures and possible gaps in knowledge on programming concepts for individual students, while existing KT methods that only analyze response correctness cannot. The bottom part shows an example from a different question. While the code prediction is less accurate than the other two examples, OKT can still capture the main logic and most important parts of the student’s actual code. From this example, it is clear how the student makes a mistake in this question and OKT is able to successfully predict that. These results show that OKT can potentially be used to provide automated feedback to both students and instructors.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have taken the first step towards open-ended knowledge tracing with applications in the computer science education domain and programming questions. Avenues for future work include exploring the limit of exact code prediction accuracy, testing different response generation pipelines, and most importantly, developing ways to use OKT to provide meaningful feedback to students and instructors.

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Figure 2: Visualization of student latent knowledge states (best viewed in color; each color corresponds to one student). Top Middle: visualization of the corresponding knowledge states for all student submissions. Top Left: zoomed-in views of two clusters and the corresponding student code where student codes in each cluster are similar. Top Right: trajectories of all attempts for two selected students that used a similar approach. Bottom: four sample submissions of two students in the top right figures. One student gradually proceeded to a correct code while the other got stuck.

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predicted code	actual student code
<pre>public String zipZip(String str) { for (int i = 0; i < str.length()- 2; i++) { if (str.charAt(i) == 'z' && str.charAt(i + 2) == 'p') { str.replace("", str.substring(i + 1)); } } return str; }</pre>	<pre>public String zipZip(String str) { for (int i = 0; i < str.length() - 2; i++) { if (str.charAt(i) == 'z' && str.charAt(i + 2) == 'p') { str.replace("0", str.substring(i + 1)); return str; } } return str; }</pre>
<pre>public String zipZip(String str) { String newStr = ""; int i = 0; while(i < str.length()) { String strA = Character.toString(str.charAt(i)); if ((str.charAt(i) == 'z') && (str.charAt(i+2) == 'p')) { newStr = newStr.concat("zp"); i = i+3; } else { newStr = newStr.concat(strA); i++; } } return newStr; }</pre>	<pre>public String zipZip(String str) { String newStr = ""; int i = 0; while(i < str.length()) { String strA = Character.toString(str.charAt(i)); if (i < str.length()-2){ if ((str.charAt(i) == 'z') && (str.charAt(i+2) == 'p')) { newStr = newStr.concat("zp"); i = i+3; } else { newStr = newStr.concat(strA); i++; } } } return newStr; }</pre>
<pre>public boolean evenlySpaced(int a, int b, int c) { int diffone = b - a; int difftwo = c - b; if (diffone == difftwo) { return true; } else { return false; } }</pre>	<pre>public boolean evenlySpaced(int a, int b, int c) { int diffone = b - a; int difftwo = c - b; boolean question = false; if (diffone == difftwo) { question = true; return question; } else { return question; } }</pre>

Table 3: OKT generated code vs. actual student code for two questions. The differences are highlighted in red boxes.

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